

ASSESSING THE ROLE OF ERP SYSTEMS IN ENSURING THE FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY OF INDUSTRIAL CLUSTERS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The article reveals the role of ERP systems in ensuring the financial sustainability of industrial clusters in Uzbekistan and suggests areas for their practical application. A conclusion was made on the need for a phased implementation of ERP, data standardization and integration with the treasury.*

Keywords: *ERP; financial sustainability; industrial cluster; internal control; risk management; Uzbekistan; cotton and textile cluster.*

In the context of global digitalization and rapid growth in information volumes, issues of ensuring the financial sustainability of industrial clusters are of particular importance. For Uzbekistan, where clusters have become one of the key forms of organizing production and interaction between enterprises in recent years, this problem is of a strategic nature. Cotton-textile, construction, pharmaceutical and agro-industrial clusters act as drivers of economic growth, forming new value chains and strengthening the country's position in world markets. However, sustainable development of clusters is impossible without a reliable system for managing financial flows and reducing risks.

Modern challenges - such as currency fluctuations, credit risks, unfair competition, and insufficient transparency of financial transactions - force enterprises to implement digital solutions that allow them to effectively manage resources. One of such solutions is ERP systems (Enterprise Resource Planning), which provide comprehensive automation of enterprise and cluster management. The use of ERP platforms allows not only to increase the efficiency of production and logistics processes, but also to significantly enhance the level of financial sustainability by monitoring cash flows, controlling debts and forecasting financial risks [1].

The relevance of the study is determined by a number of factors. Firstly, in Uzbekistan there is an active state policy on digitalization of the economy and the introduction of information technologies in the management of industrial clusters. Secondly, financial sustainability is one of the basic elements of economic sustainability and sustainable development, which is enshrined in the strategic documents of the country's development. Thirdly, the insufficient level of digitalization of accounting and management accounting in a number of clusters reduces their resilience to external and internal threats.

The scientific problem is that ERP systems, despite their widespread use in international practice, are not yet sufficiently adapted to the specifics of cluster development in Uzbekistan. There are no unified approaches to assessing their impact on financial sustainability, as well as methodological recommendations for integrating ERP into the industrial cluster management system.

The functional capabilities of ERP for ensuring financial sustainability can be identified (Figure):

Figure. ERP functionality in ensuring financial sustainability

Source: systematized by the author based on a study of ERP functionality to ensure financial sustainability.

The figure clearly demonstrates that the implementation of ERP systems has a complex impact on the financial sustainability of industrial clusters. Automation of processes allows speeding up data processing and reducing costs. Transparency of financial flows ensures control over the movement of resources and reduces corruption risks. Minimization of errors and abuses increases trust between cluster participants and external partners [2].

The next stages — risk control and liquidity forecasting — contribute to the timely adoption of management decisions, which is especially important in unstable conditions. Cost reduction creates additional stability, and the cumulative effect is expressed in strengthening the financial sustainability of clusters [3].

Thus, the ERP system acts as a link between digital management tools and ensuring the stability of financial flows in industry.

2. Current state of ERP implementation in industrial clusters of Uzbekistan:

- the most active implementation is observed in textile and construction clusters;
 - low level of digitalization remains in agro-industrial clusters;
 - limited use of ERP analytical modules for forecasting and risk management.
- ## 3. Effects of ERP implementation for financial sustainability:
- reduction of the probability of errors and distortions in financial reporting;
 - increase in the transparency of financial transactions and management decisions;
 - minimization of the risks of corruption and theft;
 - ensuring a more accurate calculation of the cost price and profitability of products.

A comparison of international and internal experience shows that ERP systems are an important tool not only for automating management processes, but also for ensuring the financial sustainability of enterprises. In developed countries, ERP is actively used to manage risks and ensure compliance with international standards, while in Uzbekistan their implementation is still primarily of an accounting nature.

The main problems of ERP implementation in industrial clusters of Uzbekistan include:

- *high cost of licenses and implementation;*
- *lack of qualified personnel capable of working with modern ERP;*
- *weak integration between enterprises within the cluster;*
- *limited access to international platforms and dependence on local solutions.*

ERP systems are an important tool for increasing the financial sustainability of industrial clusters, ensuring transparency and reliability of financial flows, minimizing risks and increasing manageability. In order to significantly enhance the sustainability of clusters, increase competitiveness and integration into the global economy, the following should be fulfilled in the conditions of Uzbekistan[^]

- Consider the implementation of an ERP system as a key factor in ensuring the financial sustainability of industrial clusters in Uzbekistan.
- Integrate accounting, production and analytical processes using ERP to increase the transparency and manageability of financial flows.
- Use ERP to eliminate financial risks, minimize losses and prevent abuse.
- Adapt ERP functionality to industry-specific clusters, paying special attention to the cotton-textile and construction sectors.
- Implement modern ERP platforms in the field of big data and artificial intelligence to predict threats and form anti-crisis principles.
- Provide state support for digitalization processes and stimulate the use of ERP to create information space management clusters.
- Consider ERP technologies not only as an automation tool, but also as a strategic mechanism for increasing the financial stability and competitiveness of clusters.

To achieve these goals, government support measures, the development of national ERP platforms and the training of qualified personnel are necessary. Thus, ERP can become a key element in the strategy for ensuring the financial sustainability of industrial clusters in Uzbekistan.

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